

The role of thiol-based complexes in modern neurosurgical practice

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Abstract

Introduction: Neuropathic pain is a common and significantly disabling condition following spinal surgery, particularly in patients with persistent radiculopathy. Effective postoperative treatment remains a challenge, with increasing interest in adjuvant therapies, including dietary supplements with neuroprotective potential, such as the Thiolin Complex.

Objective: To evaluate the clinical effect of Thiolin Complex—a dietary supplement containing alpha-lipoic acid, essential fatty acids, selenium, and B-group vitamins—on the intensity of neuropathic pain and radiculopathy in patients presenting with postoperative neurological complaints.

Materials and methods: The study included 71 patients (31 men aged between 21 and 71 years and 40 women aged between 33 and 85 years) with clinically diagnosed pain of neurological origin. The intensity of the pain syndrome was assessed by the Numeric Pain Rating Scale self-assessment scale before and 60 days after taking Thiolin Complex.

Results: In 83.1% of patients, a significant reduction in pain was observed after 60 days of Thiolin Complex. In 13 patients, the pain completely disappeared, and in 35 patients, significant relief of the pain syndrome was reported. In 11 patients, no effect was reported, and one patient reported worsening. There was no statistically significant difference in effectiveness according to gender or age group.

Conclusion: Thiolin Complex demonstrates clinical effect as an adjunct to standard therapy, which includes a drug from the group of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, in persistent postoperative neuropathic pain and hypoesthesia. The combination of anti-oxidant and neurotropic constituents promotes the recovery of the peripheral nervous system. The results suggest the applicability of the product in neurosurgical practice, with further randomized studies needed to confirm the observed effects.

Keywords

peripheral nerves, radiculopathy, alpha-lipoic acid, postoperative peripheral nerve recovery, pharmacological therapy, B-group vitamins

Introduction

Neuropathic pain, resulting from damage or dysfunction of the peripheral nervous system, represents a serious challenge in contemporary neurosurgical practice. Patients undergoing interventions for disc herniation or spinal canal stenosis often experience persistent postoperative symptoms, including radiculopathy and other forms of peripheral neuropathy, leading to chronic pain, motor disturbances, and impaired quality of life (Abdelrahman and Hackshaw 2021; Okdahl and Brock 2021). Managing these conditions requires a multidisciplinary approach involving pharmacotherapy, rehabilitation, and, increasingly, supplementation with agents possessing antioxidant and neuroprotective potential (Abdelrahman and Hackshaw 2021).

In recent years, there has been growing scientific and clinical interest in the use of neuroprotective dietary supplements as adjunct therapies for chronic neuropathic pain. This trend is driven by the limitations of conventional pharmacological treatments, particularly in addressing persistent symptoms following spinal surgeries. Compounds with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuromodulatory properties are being actively investigated for their potential to modulate pain pathways, improve neuronal resilience, and enhance quality of life. Nutritional approaches involving alpha-lipoic acid, B vitamins, polyunsaturated fatty acids, and trace elements like selenium have shown promise in reducing neuropathic symptoms and restoring nerve function, positioning such supplements as a valuable addition to integrative pain management strategies (Yorek 2018; Carreau et al. 2020; Suwannasom et al. 2020; Abdelrahman and Hackshaw 2021; Baltrusch 2021; Chuar et al. 2021; Miao et al. 2021; Okdahl and Brock 2021; Pacini et al. 2021; Stach et al. 2021; Ungurianu et al. 2021; Kharitonova et al. 2022; Rumora et al. 2022; Hsieh et al. 2023; Khobrani et al. 2023; Mrowicka et al. 2023; Muhamad et al. 2023; Zhang et al. 2023; Frediani et al. 2024; Hamoudi et al. 2024; Nguyen et al. 2024; Scholefield et al. 2024; Superti and Russo 2024; Xu et al. 2024).

Thiolin Complex (TC) is a dietary supplement containing a synergistic combination of alpha-lipoic acid, gamma-linolenic and linoleic acids, selenium methionine, and vitamins B1, B2, B5, B6, and E. This composition reflects modern trends in the management of neuropathic pain, targeting the reduction of oxidative stress, improvement of microcirculation, and restoration of metabolic activity in damaged neurons (Abdelrahman and Hackshaw 2021; Pacini et al. 2021; Hsieh et al. 2023; Nguyen et al. 2024).

Data from numerous meta-analyses and clinical studies confirm the beneficial effects of alpha-lipoic acid in patients with diabetic polyneuropathy and chronic lower back pain (Pacini et al. 2021; Hsieh et al. 2023; Nguyen et al. 2024). Combined with polyunsaturated fatty acids, such as gamma-linolenic acid, the effect is enhanced through anti-inflammatory and membrane-stabilizing actions on peripheral nerves (Yorek 2018; Rumora et al. 2022; Superti and Russo 2024). B-group vitamins, particularly B1, B2, B5, and B6, play a crucial role in neurometabolic

processes and have the potential to promote neuroplasticity and regeneration of damaged neurons (Carreau et al. 2020; Suwannasom et al. 2020; Baltrusch 2021; Stach et al. 2021; Kharitonova et al. 2022; Khobrani et al. 2023; Mrowicka et al. 2023; Muhamad et al. 2023; Hamoudi et al. 2024; Scholefield et al. 2024). Selenium contributes to antioxidant defense mechanisms by being an integral part of glutathione peroxidase, thereby enhancing neuronal resilience under oxidative stress, a common feature of chronic neuropathy (Zhang et al. 2023; Xu et al. 2024).

The aim of this study is to assess the effectiveness of Thiolin Complex in patients with postoperative neuropathic pain persisting after surgical interventions in the lumbar spine. By monitoring the dynamics of pain intensity before and 60 days after initiation of therapy with TC, the study seeks to establish the role of this supplement in the comprehensive recovery of the peripheral nervous system.

Materials and methods

The present prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Neurosurgery, University Hospital “Pulmed,” Plovdiv, to evaluate the effectiveness of Thiolin Complex on pain syndrome of neurological origin and persistent radiculopathy in patients with postoperative neurological symptoms. Patients who reported neuropathic pain, as assessed by the numeric pain rating scale (NPRS), and persistent radiculopathy in the postoperative period answered questions from a pre-designed questionnaire in the presence of their treating physician. In this observational study, the co-authors independently assessed the patients using the parameters set by the questionnaire before taking Thiolin Complex and again 60 days after initiating the dietary supplement. The same questionnaire was applied in both instances.

A total of 71 patients were included in the study over a period of one year—31 men aged between 21 and 71 years and 40 women aged between 33 and 85 years. All participants had undergone surgery in the Department of Neurosurgery at Pulmed University Hospital, most frequently for lumbar disc herniation or spinal canal stenosis. During the postoperative and recovery periods, these patients reported persistent pain of neurological etiology and concomitant radiculopathy. Patients without such complaints in the postoperative period were excluded from the observational study and did not receive the dietary supplement Thiolin Complex.

Inclusion criteria for the study were as follows: patients who, according to the NPRS, had moderate to severe pain syndrome of neurological origin and radiculopathy persisting after surgical intervention. Participants were required to be free of active infection, cancer, or other systemic inflammatory conditions; the presence of such clinical conditions led to exclusion from the study. Patients also had to be in stable general condition and must not have taken other medications with a similar composition in the 30 days prior to participation.

Pain was assessed using the numeric pain rating scale (NPRS)—a self-rating scale from 0 to 10, where:

- 0–3 indicates no pain or mild pain;
- 4–7 indicates moderate pain;
- 8–10 indicates severe to unbearable pain.

The NPRS is an internationally recognized tool used to assess pain intensity in both clinical practice and research settings. It is designed to standardize communication between patients and healthcare professionals by providing a simple numerical format for reporting pain severity. Patients are asked to rate their pain on a scale from 0 (no pain) to 10 (worst possible pain), facilitating a shared understanding of the patient’s subjective experience and enabling consistent monitoring of treatment outcomes across time and clinical contexts.

Each participant was informed in advance and gave verbal consent to participate in a survey assessing the efficacy of the dietary supplement Thiolin Complex after surgical manipulation. Pain scores according to the NPRS and the presence of hypoesthesia were evaluated by the investigators prior to administration of the supplement. All patients then took Thiolin Complex orally, once daily for 60 consecutive days. After this period, re-evaluation was performed using the same scale. Additionally, the distribution of patients by sex and age group was analyzed according to World Health Organization (WHO) classifications. According to the WHO, age groups are commonly defined to facilitate demographic and clinical research, as well as to ensure consistency in public health reporting.

This framework is widely used in clinical studies to analyze age-related trends in disease presentation, treatment outcomes, and patient responses to therapies. No additional patient-specific data were used in this study beyond those discussed in the text.

Analysis of the results included both qualitative (percentage of responders with improvement) and quantitative (comparison of mean pain scores before and after therapy) parameters. Statistical analysis to assess significance between groups by sex and age was performed using descriptive statistics.

Results

To determine the supportive and potentially therapeutic effects of Thiolin Complex in managing neurologically derived pain syndrome, data were collected and analyzed from 71 patients—specifically, 31 men aged between 21 and 71 years and 40 women aged between 33 and 85 years. The inclusion criterion for the study was the persistence of neurological pain in the patients.

For the purpose of analyzing the collected data, patients were divided into age groups based on the World Health Organization (WHO) classification, which defines 0–14 years as childhood, 15–44 years as youth, 45–59 years as middle (mature) age, 60–74 years as elderly, 75–89 years as old age, and 90 years and above as longevity. It is clearly evident that the majority of patients in this study were aged between 60 and 74 years, i.e., in the „elderly“ category (Figs 1, 2).

Figure 1. Distribution of patients taking Thiolin Complex by gender.

Figure 2. Distribution of patients taking Thiolin Complex by age category.

This study followed the effect of Thiolin Complex in all 71 patients, measuring the level of pain syndrome before treatment and 60 days after initiating the product. Pain was measured in two ways—through the self-assessment Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) and by evaluating the reduction in absolute pain values. The NPRS rates pain from 0 to 10, where scores from 0 to 3 indicate no pain or mild pain, scores from 4 to 7 indicate moderate pain, and scores from 8 to 10 indicate the most severe pain possible. Each patient was asked to complete a questionnaire before starting treatment, in which they had to indicate the number corresponding to the intensity of their pain.

In evaluating the results of the therapy, an analysis was also conducted on the reduction of pain in absolute value. Before starting treatment:

- 21 patients reported mild pain (2–3 points on the scale);
- 49 patients reported moderate pain (4–7 points on the scale);
- One patient reported severe pain (8 points on the scale).

Table 1. Before starting the intake of the Thiolin Complex.

Before starting the intake of the Thiolin Complex	
21 patients	2 to 3 points (mild pain)
49 patients	from 4 to 7 (moderate pain)
1 patient	from 8 to 10 (the most severe pain)

The Figs 3, 4 present the number and percentage of patients who experienced a change in pain intensity during therapy with Thiolin Complex.

Figure 3. Is the patient positively affected after the therapy? (number of patients).

As observed in the above figures (Figs 3, 4), 59 patients reported improvement in their pain syndrome, representing 83.1% of all surveyed patients. In 11 patients (15.5%), no improvement was reported, and in 1 patient (1.4%), the pain worsened.

Figure 4. Is the patient positively affected after the therapy? (percentage, relative to the total number).

An analysis of absolute changes in pain scores before and after taking Thiolin Complex was conducted. Sixty days after initiation of treatment (Fig. 5), 13 patients (18.3%) reported a pain score of 0 on the Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), indicating complete absence of pain. Additionally, 35 patients (49.3%) experienced a reduction in pain intensity to a score between 1 and 2, corresponding to minimal residual pain. In 11 patients (15.5%), pain levels decreased but remained within the moderate range (NPRS 4–7), while in another 11 patients (15.5%) no change was observed. One patient (1.4%) reported an increase in pain intensity. These data suggest that more than two-thirds of patients achieved either complete or near-complete pain relief, defined quantitatively as an NPRS score of 2 or below (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. NPRS Score after 60 days of uptake.

In half of the participants, pain and hypoesthesia were significantly reduced, and in another 13 patients, they were completely eliminated after 60 days of taking the product. The data show no statistically significant correlation between gender or age group and the effectiveness of the therapy, suggesting the universality of the observed therapeutic effect.

Discussion

Chronic postoperative pain (CPSP) is a significant problem affecting 10–20% of patients following surgery for lumbar disc herniation or spinal stenosis in the lumbar region, with 2–10% of cases classified as moderate to severe, often leading to functional limitations and psychological complications. Approximately 35–50% of patients with CPSP exhibit neuropathic pain characteristics, underscoring the importance of neuroprotective nutritional supplements in surgical practice (Yorek 2018; Carreau et al. 2020; Suwannasom et al. 2020; Abdelrahman and Hackshaw 2021; Baltrusch 2021; Chuar et al. 2021; Miao et al. 2021; Okdahl and Brock 2021; Pacini et al. 2021; Stach et al. 2021; Ungurianu et al. 2021; Kharitonova et al. 2022; Rumora et al. 2022; Hsieh et al. 2023; Khoibrani et al. 2023; Koivunen et al. 2023; Mrowicka et al. 2023; Muhamad et al. 2023; Zhang et al. 2023; Frediani et al. 2024; Hamoudi et al. 2024; Nguyen et al. 2024; Scholefield et al. 2024; Superti and Russo 2024; Xu et al. 2024). During surgery, mechanical traction of peripheral nerves triggers a cascade of inflammatory and neuronal responses, leading to hypoesthesia in the corresponding dermatome. Primary afferents release pro-inflammatory mediators that increase neuronal excitability (Yorek 2018; Carreau et al. 2020; Suwannasom et al. 2020; Baltrusch 2021; Chuar et al. 2021; Miao et al. 2021; Okdahl and Brock 2021; Pacini et al. 2021; Stach et al. 2021; Ungurianu et al. 2021; Kharitonova et al. 2022; Rumora et al. 2022; Hsieh et al. 2023; Khoibrani et al. 2023; Koivunen et al. 2023; Mrowicka et al. 2023; Muhamad et al. 2023; Zhang et al. 2023; Frediani et al. 2024; Hamoudi et al. 2024; Nguyen et al. 2024; Scholefield et al. 2024; Superti and Russo 2024; Xu et al. 2024).

Thiolin Complex (TC) is a dietary supplement that contains a combination of vitamins and essential fatty acids—alpha-lipoic acid, gamma-linolenic and linoleic acids, selenomethionine, as well as vitamins B1, B2, B5, B6, and E. According to the literature, combining conventional pharmacological treatments for idiopathic neuropathic pain with nutritional supplementation and physical activity is considered an optimal approach for managing this condition (Abdelrahman and Hackshaw 2021). In addition, TC may be used as an adjuvant therapy in diabetic polyneuropathy due to the demonstrated beneficial effects of its components (Okdahl and Brock 2021). In the following paragraphs, we present the pharmacological actions of the individual components of TC and their long-term effects on peripheral nerves. The study group comprises patients who underwent surgery for disc pathology or spinal canal stenosis in the lower lumbar segment, in whom TC was used to support the recovery of the peripheral nervous system.

Alpha-lipoic acid (ALA) is an antioxidant derived from caprylic acid. It is produced in the mitochondria and participates in the elimination of reactive oxygen species (ROS) through its two forms—oxidized lipoic acid and reduced dihydrolipoic acid (Nguyen et al. 2024). ALA eliminates reactive oxygen and nitrogen species, regenerates other antioxidants (vitamin C, vitamin E, and glutathione), and

modulates the NF- κ B signaling pathway, thereby reducing the synthesis of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β and TNF- α (Abdelrahman and Hackshaw 2021; Okdahl and Brock 2021; Nguyen et al. 2024). It is rapidly metabolized in the liver, with a plasma half-life of approximately 30 minutes when taken orally; however, activation of endogenous enzymes extends its therapeutic effect (Okdahl and Brock 2021; Nguyen et al. 2024). In cases of radiculopathy, oxidative stress increases due to reactive gliosis and astrocyte proliferation in the dorsal horns of the spinal cord, resulting in ROS accumulation and sensory hyperexcitability. By reducing ROS, ALA helps restore normal sensory neuron function and stabilizes astrocytes (Pacini et al. 2021). Additionally, ALA improves microcirculation in distal nerves and enhances sensory function in diabetic polyneuropathy (Hsieh et al. 2023).

Linoleic and gamma-linolenic fatty acids are polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) that belong to the omega-6 group. They are classified as essential fatty acids because they cannot be synthesized by the human body and must be obtained through the diet (Yorek 2018). Gamma-linolenic acid (GLA) serves as a precursor to prostaglandin derivatives that suppress pro-inflammatory PGE2 and TXA2 while promoting the production of anti-inflammatory PGE1. The action of PUFAs includes balancing the biosynthesis of new lipids in Schwann cells, which form the myelin sheath around peripheral nerve axons, and maintaining normal levels of gangliosides and cerebroside that stabilize the cell membrane. Additionally, PUFAs support the function and metabolite transport of axonal mitochondria, thereby reducing ROS formation (Rumora et al. 2022). In cases of radiculopathy, Ranieri et al. demonstrated a significant enhancement of treatment efficacy with a combination of ALA and gamma-linolenic acid compared to monotherapy with rehabilitative agents, most likely due to their anti-inflammatory effects (Superti and Russo 2024).

Vitamin E is a fat-soluble vitamin composed of four tocopherols and four tocotrienols, known for their potent antioxidant effects. Regular intake has been associated with a reduced risk of chronic inflammation, as well as endocrine, cardiovascular, and neurodegenerative disorders. The role of vitamin E is related to its ability to decrease tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), several interleukins, and pro-inflammatory prostaglandins. Clinical studies have shown that higher blood levels of certain forms of vitamin E are associated with improved cognitive function in Alzheimer's disease and a reduced accumulation of β -amyloid (Ungurianu et al. 2021). By decreasing ROS levels, vitamin E supplementation also alleviates the symptoms of diabetic polyneuropathy (Chuar et al. 2021). The prevention of oxidative stress is also believed to underlie the beneficial effects of vitamin E on chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy, such as that caused by cisplatin (Miao et al. 2021).

Vitamin B1, also known as thiamine, was the first discovered among the water-soluble vitamins in this group. It acts as a cofactor in numerous enzymatic pathways related to glucose metabolism, lactate processing, and normal

mitochondrial function. A deficiency of vitamin B1 in neurons leads to the inactivation of dependent enzymes, disrupting energy production and generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) that impair structural and functional cellular integrity. Furthermore, decreased production of steroids and fatty acids results in significant demyelination. Thiamine inhibits acetylcholinesterase, thereby prolonging the presence of acetylcholine in synapses and enhancing neuronal circuit function (Mrowicka et al. 2023). According to literature data, vitamin B1 supports the regeneration of mechanically damaged nerve roots and reduces hyperexcitability—manifested as pain and sensory disturbances—likely due to the normalization of carbohydrate metabolism (Baltrusch 2021).

Vitamin B2 (riboflavin) is a water-soluble essential nutrient known for its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Because the human body cannot store vitamin B2, it must be regularly obtained through diet and/or oral supplementation. Its two metabolically active forms—flavin mononucleotide (FMN) and flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD)—function as coenzymes in numerous redox reactions. Riboflavin enhances the activity of cellular antioxidant enzymes such as glutathione peroxidase, catalase, and superoxide dismutase (Suwannasom et al. 2020). When combined with other antioxidants, vitamin B2 has shown beneficial effects on the symptoms of diabetic polyneuropathy, particularly paresthesia (Khari-tonova et al. 2022). Deficiencies in riboflavin transporters can result in severe peripheral neuropathies, which are partially alleviated through high-dose supplementation, highlighting its crucial role in neuronal and axonal function (Carreau et al. 2020).

Vitamin B5, also known as pantothenic acid (PA), is a precursor for the synthesis of coenzyme A (CoA), which plays a central role in the metabolism of fatty acids, carbohydrates, and amino acids. Like other B vitamins, it is water-soluble, exhibits antioxidant activity, and cannot be stored in the body for extended periods. Given CoA's involvement in a broad range of biochemical processes (estimated at approximately 4% of all cellular reactions), regular intake of PA is essential for maintaining normal physiological function. Reduced levels of PA have been observed in neurodegenerative disorders such as Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease (Scholefield et al. 2024). Additionally, rare cases of PA deficiency due to malnutrition can result in neuropathic pain, often described as “burning sensations in the affected limbs.” Clinical trials in *Drosophila* models have demonstrated improved thermal sensitivity following vitamin B5 administration, suggesting a potential role in modulating chronic pain in humans (Hamoudi et al. 2024).

Vitamin B6 comprises three water-soluble compounds—pyridoxal, pyridoxamine, and pyridoxine—along with their phosphorylated forms. Of these, pyridoxal phosphate is the primary biologically active form, serving as a cofactor in a wide range of biochemical reactions. Medically, its role in enhancing immune function is of particular interest; it reduces cytokine storms and promotes

T-lymphocyte production. Deficiency in vitamin B6 is associated with immunodeficiency, as well as increased risk of atherosclerosis and thrombotic events (Stach et al. 2021). Khobrani et al. reported that more than 50% of patients with diabetic polyneuropathy exhibited pyridoxine deficiency (Kho-brani et al. 2023). The role of vitamin B6 in peripheral nerve injury remains controversial, as studies report varying outcomes—ranging from symptom improvement to the development of sensory neuropathy with excessive intake. Nevertheless, therapeutic doses of vitamin B6, when administered in combination with other B-group vitamins and antioxidants, have not been associated with adverse effects (Muhamad et al. 2023).

Selenium is an essential micronutrient involved in immune modulation, lipid metabolism, and the reduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Its primary biological functions are carried out through selenoproteins, whose metabolic activity depends on selenocysteine residues—often referred to as the 21st amino acid in the human body. Selenium is particularly important for normal brain function, as it inhibits ferroptosis in neurons, supports neuronal development, and regulates certain neurotransmitters, including gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) (Zhang et al. 2023). Like other essential nutrients, selenium levels are often reduced in patients with diabetic polyneuropathy and are associated with decreased nerve conduction velocity. Given selenium's role as a component of the active site in glutathione peroxidase, supplementation may help reduce oxidative stress in axons and improve clinical outcomes in such patients (Xu et al. 2024).

The pharmacological profile of the components of Thiolin Complex—including alpha-lipoic acid, polyunsaturated fatty acids, B vitamins, vitamin E, and selenium—supports the clinical findings observed in this study. Numerous studies have demonstrated that these compounds exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, membrane-stabilizing, and neuroprotective effects, which are particularly relevant in conditions involving chronic oxidative stress and peripheral nerve damage.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that the use of thiol-based complexes as an adjunct to standard therapy in patients with postoperative neuropathic pain associated with radiculopathy from spinal disorders led to a reduction in pain syndrome in 83.1% of the observed patients. Although this was not a randomized clinical trial, the study provides valuable observational data regarding the tolerability and potential benefits of neuroprotective nutritional supplements in routine neurosurgical practice.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

The authors analyzed the results and compared them with data from the literature. We did an original study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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